

Readiness of senior high school grade 12 ABM students in Batangas City to take an accounting degree in college

Jehara Mae D. Nicolas, Cheenie M. Andal, Ellen May B. Ariola, Cristen N. De Castro, Shaine F. Fallan,
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Abstract

This study assessed the readiness of senior high school grade 12 ABM students in Batangas City to take an accounting degree in college. The study sought to know the extent of college readiness and measure the skills of Grade 12 ABM students, to know the significant relationship between the readiness of ABM grade 12 students and ABM skills, the challenges that students encountered, and to develop an action plan based on the findings. The researchers utilized a descriptive research design with the use of stratified random sampling and used the self-made constructed questionnaire as the main instrument in the study. The gathered data were treated using statistical tools. The source materials used were from the internet to gather the needed data. The findings showed that the majority of students agreed that they were ready to take an accounting degree in college in terms of cognitive strategies, content knowledge, academic behavior, and contextual skills and awareness. The measurement of Grade 12 ABM skills in terms of critical thinking, collaboration, creativity, and communication results as moderately high, indicating that students were in an excellent position to pursue an accounting degree in college. The readiness of ABM grade 12 students had a positive correlation with ABM skills. The challenges resulted in ABM students experiencing different situations that often affected their academic performance. The action plan aimed to improve the Four Facets of College Readiness, 4C's of 21st Century Learning Skills, and ABM students' challenges. The objectives targeted the items with the lowest scores for each area. A success indicator was added to determine its effectivity.

Keywords: Readiness; senior high school; accounting degree; Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM); students.

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Introduction

Students can be prepared for tertiary education through secondary education, which serves as a foundation for them to pursue their desired program. Given the significance of education in this, there are several factors that schools should take into account to improve students' knowledge and skills for successfully navigating the paths to and through college. Being prepared for college is a key component of students' education. It can help them become more conscious of and ready for college while also giving them a head start on their endeavors. The development of fundamental skills including writing, reading, science, and mathematics among undergraduate students in the late 1800s marked the beginning of the history of college readiness (Almeida, 2015). The methods for college readiness place a strong emphasis on how students perceive fundamental academic material as well as cognitive, non-cognitive, and learning strategies (Duncheon, 2015).

There are several issues with student achievement and retention in higher education all throughout the world. Because it gauges how well-prepared students are for success after secondary school, college and career readiness is a contentious topic in the United States. It is challenging for students to make the academic and social adjustments required to effectively complete high school and enroll in college since they still need assistance in preparing for college and careers. Over the past few decades, the Standards Admissions Test (SAT) and the American College Test (ACT) have developed into crucial components of the college application process in the United States, providing accurate and valuable data about students' academic readiness and suitability for highly selective colleges. However, those exams have lost some of their luster in recent years. According to Roderick et al. (2009), more than 80% of high school seniors want to pursue four-year degrees. However, only a small percentage of students enroll in degree-granting initiatives within a year of high school graduation. About 36% of students need remedial action because they need to prepare for college-level coursework.

In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) introduced the K-12 program. This program extended the senior high school's primary education. They had enough time as a result to fully comprehend the ideas in their preferred courses. There are five tracks available in the K-12 senior high school curriculum: academic, arts and design, sports, technical, and vocational. The goal of this fundamental reform is to simplify the course offerings so that students can learn 21st-century competencies, including literacy, critical thinking, and technical skills.

The DepEd conducted the Basic Education Exit Assessment (BEEA) solely to assess the abilities learned by students in Grades 11 and 12; thus, this was governed by DepEd Order No. 5, Series 2019 (Administration of the Basic Education Exit Assessment for School Year 2018-2019); DepEd Order No. 25, s. 2018; and DepEd Order No. 55, s. 2016 (Policy Guidelines on the National Assessment of Student Learning for the K-12 Basic Education Program). However, it does not determine whether or not senior high school graduates are college ready. The Basic Education Exit Assessment (BEEA) was administered to the first two batches of senior high school students. According to briefing data, these students received mean percentage scores of 36.71 and 36.45 (Villonez, 2018). When evaluating how well students' competencies match their level of college preparedness, the omission of a college readiness test creates a gap.

In 2011, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) introduced College Readiness Standards (CRS) to highlight the capabilities that K-12 graduates intended to achieve and master as critical entry competences in college. To date, no standardized college readiness test (CRT) has been developed in the Philippines to assess these graduates' preparedness and potential success based on the CHED's CRS, so first-year college students are admitted solely based on arbitrary criteria. As a result of the current situation, several opinions exist on what defines college-ready, which may or may not reflect the competences achieved by senior high school graduates as defined by the CRS (Tamayao et al., 2020).

For various reasons, few students have the courage to enroll in accountancy, business, and management (ABM), which is thought to be one of the most difficult courses. Studying accounting involves a large time commitment, and the burden will increase as courses move forward (Samsuddin et al., 2015). Byrne et al. (2012) claimed that accounting students' assessments of their preparation for college play a significant role in how successfully they adapt to the university learning environment. Unfortunately, many accounting students require assistance because they are unsure of what is expected of them in higher education. They bring epistemological presumptions from their earlier schooling, where learning was typically associated with the passive assimilation of outside knowledge, to college. According to Wingate (2007), higher education necessitates the development of critical thinking skills as well as the integration and application of information in many situations. Furthermore, ABM students must have cognitive strategies, skills, and knowledge in order to prepare for a college accounting degree. This can assist them in obtaining their desired occupation. As a result, preparation is essential since it inspires accounting students to pursue higher education.

Magnaye (2020) focused on the eight public senior high schools that offer the ABM component in Batangas City, which has one of the highest literacy rates in the Philippines. Magnaye (2020) said that the actual readiness of Batangas City students for college and future employment is highly questionable. Although the students' self-perceptions suggested that they were intellectually, socially, and emotionally prepared for college, there are still areas of social-emotional and intellectual preparation that need to be improved. More than just educating them for college is needed to offer them a better career after they finish their education.

Self-reported responses may be overstated, and respondents may feel embarrassed to provide sensitive information. The limitations of the study are that some of the students were unwilling to participate in the survey and were unsure about disclosing information. Some were unable to comprehend the terminologies used in the questionnaire completely. The goal of research is to produce knowledge that can be applied as widely as possible. However, since it is usually not possible to analyze every member of a population, researchers make do by analyzing and making statements about that portion. To apply these statements to larger groups, researchers must ensure that the sample accurately resembles the broader population. The study focused on assessing the readiness of senior high school Grade 12 ABM students in Batangas City. The factors used may affect the accuracy and comparability of the academic readiness of each respondent.

Thus, this study aimed to assess the readiness of senior high school Grade 12 accountancy, business, and management (ABM) students to take accounting degrees in college. The researchers aspired to determine the relationship between the Grade 12 ABM students' skills and their readiness to take an accounting degree. This study also paved the way for providing insights, specific guidelines, and information to senior high schools to improve their management concerning students' readiness for college and develop a proposed action plan to assist them in preparing for an accounting program in college.

According to Conley's (2007) approach, the components of academic preparedness consist of the following elements: vital cognitive strategies, key content areas, academic behaviors, and contextual skills and awareness. This framework served as the foundation and guide for this research. The study's major theoretical foundation described and assessed the readiness of senior high school Grade 12 ABM students to pursue an accounting degree in college, which includes cognitive strategies, key content areas, academic behaviors, and contextual skills and awareness. It assisted in determining and addressing college preparedness levels and aided users in nurturing and developing Grade 12 ABM students' college preparedness. These skills functioned as the instruments necessary to achieve the desired outcome of college readiness.

Conley (2007) developed the Facets of College Readiness Framework into four concentric tiers. To characterize the intellectual actions required for college readiness, the researchers chose key cognitive strategies for this framework and underlined the importance of developing these behaviors over time so that they become established ways of thinking and automatic habits related to the intellectual pursuits pursued. On the other hand, key content areas incorporated salient cognitive strategies. Two critical components of successful college academic preparation are vital cognitive strategies and content knowledge. Understanding and mastering essential content information requires using broader cognitive skills within effective cognitive strategies. Academic behaviors can be referred to as study habits. This aspect of college preparedness refers to a set of behaviors that demonstrate increased self-awareness, self-monitoring, and self-control on the part of students regarding a set of processes and behaviors required for academic achievement. Meanwhile, contextual skills and awareness go along with the system of the tertiary institution, its operation, and its rules and regulations. As a growing number of students apply to college, this broad category's importance has recently been addressed.

The objectives of the study are:

1. To ascertain the level of extent of college readiness in Senior High School in terms of cognitive strategies, content area, academic behaviour, and contextual skills and awareness.
2. To measure the skills of Grade 12 ABM students in terms of critical thinking, collaboration, creativity, and communication.
3. To determine the significant relationship between the readiness of ABM grade 12 students and ABM skills.
4. To identify the challenges ABM students, encounter when learning ABM major subjects.
5. To propose action plan to prepare Grade 12 ABM students to take an accounting degree in college.

Methodology

The descriptive research design was utilized in this study. It was the best fit since the study gathered information to describe and assess the readiness of senior high school Grade 12 ABM students to pursue an accounting degree in college. It also describes the significant relationship between the skills of Grade 12 ABM students and taking an accounting degree in college.

The subject and the respondents of the study were the Grade 12 ABM students from public senior high schools in Batangas City. The 226 sample size was calculated using the Raosoft calculator with a 5% margin of error and a 95% confidence level from the 547 population. Only 139 respondents participated in the study. The researchers used stratified random sampling techniques to gather the data.

The researchers used self-constructed questionnaires as the primary tool for data gathering, which were divided into four parts. The self-constructed questionnaire was based on the statement of the problem. The items were created by combining the researchers' reading, different sources such as research journals, concepts from the literature gathered, and information from related studies discussing the college readiness of senior high school ABM students. The opening section of the questionnaire included the study's title, which identified the subject of the study, as well as the letter to respondents explaining the study's objectives and obtaining informed consent. Disclosing the identities would remain anonymous and be used for academic purposes only, and the information gathered would be kept confidential in accordance with ethical standards and the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173).

After the contents of the questionnaire were completed, they were given to the adviser for review and approval. Next, the questionnaire was validated by the research team and industry experts. The researchers also consulted a statistician to assist with the questionnaire's improvement. The approved survey questionnaire was encoded in Google Forms and pilot tested to confirm that the desired instrument functions properly and is reliable. The accepted minimum value of Cronbach's alpha is 0.7, which indicates an acceptable level of reliability, and 0.8 or greater indicates a very good level. The pilot testing resulted in a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.943. This indicated that the survey questionnaire had strong consistency and was reliable before it was administered and distributed to the actual survey respondents.

In conducting the study, the researchers submitted a letter to the Office of School Division Superintendents requesting an endorsement letter and the total number of Grade 12 ABM students in Batangas City's public senior high schools. The researchers then started to utilize Google Forms to create questionnaires. Then, researchers sought the assistance of the teachers in obtaining responses from the respondents. They also look up students' names on their individual school pages. Following their discovery and request for assistance, the researchers delivered questionnaires to the respondents. The respondents were given clear instructions and questions. Hence, the researchers paid close attention to the online ethical considerations and only used the data for study purposes.

The collected information was statistically analyzed using a weighted mean and composite mean to measure the responses of Grade 12 ABM students to the practice of the four facets of college readiness, skills, and challenges they encounter when learning ABM major subjects. It would ensure that the indicators are independent of one another, and it should predict other indicators of the variable. Pearson R correlational analysis was also used in the study to identify the relationship between the readiness of Grade 12 ABM students to take their chosen accounting degree and their ABM skills. The perceived degree of ABM students' college readiness was evaluated using the 4-point scale.

Results and Discussion

Facets of College Readiness

The four facets of college readiness include key cognitive strategies, key content areas, academic behaviors, and contextual skills and awareness. This is used to describe and assess the readiness of senior high school Grade 12 ABM students to pursue an accounting degree in college.

1. Key Cognitive Strategies - It emphasizes the importance of developing behaviors over time to become established ways of thinking and automatic habits related to how intellectual pursuits are pursued.

Table 1. Facets of College Readiness in terms of Key Cognitive Strategies

Key Cognitive Strategies	WM	VI
1. I practice my analytical thinking by participating in recitations and teacher discussions.	3.23	A
2. I applied critical thinking to make sound decisions while analyzing case studies.	3.15	A
3. I gain knowledge through real-life scenarios introduced to us by the teacher that helps me apply it in everyday life and prepare for college.	3.42	SA
4. I position my mindsets and academics so that they are potentially enough to enter the unfamiliar terrain of college.	3.26	SA
5. I benefited from the activities and practicum during senior high school in acquiring practical knowledge that can be used and applied to college.	3.22	A
6. I don't just memorize the lesson during exams; instead, I understand it by heart and use it for actual scenarios that can be applied in college course subjects.	3.15	A
7. I tend to learn something new and apply it, making sure to process, analyze, and evaluate them.	3.32	SA
8. I practice my cognitive abilities through reading books and other materials that drive my memory to adapt to the information.	3.27	SA
Composite Mean	3.25	A

Legend: 3.26-4.00: Strongly Agree (SA); 2.51-3.25: Agree (A); 1.76-2.50: Disagree (D); 1.00-1.75: Strongly Disagree (SD); Weighted Mean (WM); Verbal Interpretation (VI)

Based on the results in Table 1, the highest weighted mean is 3.42, with a verbal interpretation of strongly agree. Conversely, the least weighted mean is 3.15 and is verbally interpreted as agree. Overall, the respondents strongly agreed on the extent of key cognitive strategies, with a composite mean of 3.25. This signifies that the Grade 12 ABM students are ready to enter the college level of education in terms of key cognitive strategies. The learner will be able to self-learn and discover new things if they successfully master the internal process (Suyitno, 2017).

2. Key Content Knowledge - This refers to the foundational understanding of academic disciplines. It is the body of knowledge and information that teachers teach. Those students are expected to understand a specific subject or content areas, such as language, arts, mathematics, science, or social studies. This can be attained and acquired by processing information, analyzing, integrating, and applying the information gathered using cognitive strategies.

Table 2. Facets of College Readiness in terms of Key Content Knowledge

Key Content Knowledge	WM	VI
1. My scientific knowledge is developed enough in facing real-world scenarios that can be applied to accounting matters as it is also considered art and science through recording, classifying, and summarizing transactions.	3.17	A
2. The experience in the arts, practical research, and feasibility studies can be a great way to prepare me for college.	3.29	SA
3. My knowledge of mathematics content such as business math, general math, and accounting fundamentals is good practice that can be used in college accounting courses.	3.27	SA
4. Work immersion is another content that helped me experience the real business world through field studies and interviews.	3.40	SA
5. Information technology laboratories allow me to practice my knowledge with Excel, PowerPoint, and Word documents which will help me easily make presentations in college courses.	3.29	SA
6. The accounting-related materials helped me learn the concepts and theories that could aid in solving problems, assignments, and other exercises.	3.29	SA
7. Writing an essay, article, poem, or anything else, is a helpful tool that helps me to organize the content properly and use appropriate words.	3.27	SA
8. Subjects like marketing, accounting, business ethics, financial management, and others are the contents that I focus on because I know it can still be used in my college courses and can also be applied in the corporate world in the future.	3.37	SA
Composite Mean	3.29	SA

Legend: 3.26-4.00: Strongly Agree (SA); 2.51-3.25: Agree (A); 1.76-2.50: Disagree (D); 1.00-1.75: Strongly Disagree (SD); Weighted Mean (WM); Verbal Interpretation (VI)

The result in Table 2 indicates that the item obtaining the highest ranking of 3.40 weighted mean was verbally interpreted as strongly agreeing. While the least weighted mean is 3.17, verbally interpreted as agree, The composite mean obtained was 3.29, which means the level of extent in terms of key content knowledge was strongly agreed upon. According to Conley (2010), as cited in Collins (2015), the foundation is foundational to understanding academic disciplines. As students enter college, they are expected to write and read constantly. They are exposed to reading materials in a format different from high school, and they need to analyze them using well-organized writing. In other words, every high school graduate must have read and write as overarching academic skills to be academically prepared.

3. Academic Behaviors – It is one of the facets of evaluating and assessing the readiness of the students who will take an accounting degree in college. These are the study habits of the Grade 12 ABM students towards their school tasks and activities that can affect their academic performance.

Table 3. Facets of College Readiness in terms of Academic Behaviors

Academic Behaviors	WM	VI
1. I am often able to collaborate and engage in class discussions and maintain a schedule for accomplishing homework and other activities on time.	3.17	A
2. I am indulging in bad study habits such as procrastination, not doing homework, not participating in class, and spending a lot of time on gadgets, which negatively impact my student performance.	2.56	A
3. I learn to manage and use my time efficiently and effectively by employing techniques like Pomodoro timers and avoiding social media usage to better focus on schoolwork.	3.22	A
4. I set priorities and goals such as listing the tasks and activities through a to-do list and formulating and implementing a strategy to have an organized schedule.	3.35	SA
5. I apply note-taking techniques in writing essential lessons and have better retention of information.	3.24	A
6. I practice and learn to take notes and get benefits as it can help me prepare for college.	3.29	SA
7. I regularly take advantage of participating in collaborative discussions to broaden my knowledge and share my perspectives on various topics, which is beneficial for college work groupings.	3.08	A
8. I have a lack of bravery to ask for and seek assistance from my professors to better comprehend the topics and discussions.	2.89	A
Composite Mean	3.10	A

Legend: 3.26-4.00: Strongly Agree (SA); 2.51-3.25: Agree (A); 1.76-2.50: Disagree (D); 1.00-1.75: Strongly Disagree (SD); Weighted Mean (WM); Verbal Interpretation (VI)

Based on the results in Table 3, the item with the highest ranking has a weighted mean of 3.35, which is verbally interpreted as strongly agree. The lowest weighted mean is 2.56, which is verbally interpreted as agree. With a composite mean of 3.10, the respondents agreed on the extent of their readiness in terms of academic behavior. To achieve collaborative work goals, teamwork and interaction are needed. According to Fouché (2017), there are various reasons why a student might be misbehaving, such as family and experiences. Credé and Kuncel (2008, as cited in Vergara et al., 2015) said that study behavior is the degree to which the student regularly engages in acts of studying defined by proper studying routines that are conducive to learning.

4. Key Contextual Skills and Awareness - This includes the students' knowledge and understanding in terms of the educational system, specifically the tertiary institution, its rules and regulations, and the norms. Table 4 presents the weighted mean, verbal interpretation, and corresponding ranking for each item listed under the facets of college readiness in terms of key contextual skills and awareness.

Based on the outcome, the item that obtained the highest ranking has a weighted mean of 3.18 and a verbal interpretation of agree. The lowest ranking got the least weighted mean of 2.71 and a verbal interpretation of agree. Considering all of this, the respondents' extent of college readiness in terms of key contextual skills and awareness was agreed upon with a composite mean of 2.95. This aspect of college readiness is essential for the students, as it can help them easily cope with and adapt to their new learning environment.

According to Conley (2007, as cited by Collins, 2015), contextual skills and awareness are the most intriguing facets of academic preparation to ensure success in college education, as they help the students possess a basic understanding of the educational system and the institution of higher education, which can help them navigate within the course that they are taking and acquire the necessary skills to adapt to their new learning environment.

Table 4. Facets of College Readiness in terms of Key Contextual Skills and Awareness

Key Contextual Skills and Awareness	WM	VI
1. I am unfamiliar with the norms of the college and its new educational systems, such as university applications, scholarships, school fees, and entrance tests.	2.79	A
2. I am not yet prepared to begin a new college degree, particularly an accounting program, because they are unsure whether to pursue it or not to owe to new educational policies.	2.71	A
3. I have high school academic experiences, which helped me cope and adapt to new environments, such as facing new people and getting overwhelmed to see facilities and structures.	3.04	A
4. I am knowledgeable about new subjects to take like learning higher accounting, as well as observing retention policies and maintaining grades.	2.83	A
5. I am ready for college since I am excited to socialize with the senior year and be motivated by their actions.	2.96	A
6. I consider the possible changes to the new instructor I will have in college.	3.18	A
7. I am prepared well for the new school environment by reading facts or articles regarding the school I want to enroll in, which enables me to adapt easily.	2.95	A
8. I ensure that I have knowledge about the new set of rules and regulations for the school I want to enroll in.	3.12	A
Composite Mean	2.95	A

Legend: 3.26-4.00: Strongly Agree (SA); 2.51-3.25: Agree (A); 1.76-2.50: Disagree (D); 1.00-1.75: Strongly Disagree (SD); Weighted Mean (WM); Verbal Interpretation (VI)

Based on the outcome, the item that obtained the highest ranking has a weighted mean of 3.18 and a verbal interpretation of agree. The lowest ranking got the least weighted mean of 2.71 and a verbal interpretation of agree. Considering all of this, the respondents' extent of college readiness in terms of key contextual skills and awareness was agreed upon with a composite mean of 2.95. This aspect of college readiness is essential for the students, as it can help them easily cope with and adapt to their new learning environment. According to Conley (2007, as cited by Collins, 2015), contextual skills and awareness are the most intriguing facets of academic preparation to ensure success in college education, as they help the students possess a basic understanding of the educational system and the institution of higher education, which can help them navigate within the course that they are taking and acquire the necessary skills to adapt to their new learning environment.

Accountancy, Business, and Management Skills

The 4C's of 21st-century learning skills were used to assess the skills of Grade 12 ABM students in terms of their readiness to pursue an accounting degree in college. It includes critical thinking, collaboration, creativity, and communication.

1. Critical Thinking - The ability to effectively conceptualize, apply, analyze, synthesize, and/or evaluate information. This is the ability of an individual to think in an organized and rational manner to comprehend connections between ideas and facts, particularly in problem-solving. Table 5 depicts 4C's of 21st-century learning skills focusing on critical thinking.

Table 5. ABM Skills in terms of Critical Thinking

Critical Thinking	WM	VI
1. Ability to analyze complex problems.	2.99	MH
2. Effectively analyze and evaluate evidence and arguments.	3.00	MH
3. Interpret information and draw a conclusion based on the best analysis.	3.00	MH
4. Make proper judgment and decisions.	3.09	MH
5. Reflect critically on learning experience processes through attention and observation.	3.14	MH
6. Solve crucial problems with either small or large pieces of knowledge and information.	3.05	MH
7. Ability to influence and change one's perspective thinking.	3.03	MH
8. Persuasively communicate observations and results through different formats with minimal effort.	3.02	MH
Composite Mean	3.04	MH

Legend: 3.26-4.00: High (H); 2.51-3.25: Moderately High (MH); 1.76-2.50: Moderately Low (ML); 1.00-1.75: Low (L); Weighted Mean (WM); Verbal Interpretation (VI)

From the table, it can be seen that the item that attained the highest ranking has a weighted mean of 3.14 and a verbal interpretation of moderately high. On the contrary, the indicator that obtained the lowest rank has a weighted mean of 2.99, which is verbally interpreted as moderately high. Thus, the respondents' level of critical thinking was moderately high, resulting in a composite mean of 3.04. The result implies that Grade 12 ABM students possess critical thinking skills, which are vital in solving problems and making proper decisions. Moreover, Adedoyin and Okere (2017) also stated that critical thinking benefits a student's life because it improves one's attention and observation of whatever they are working on.

2. Collaboration - This is important for students because it allows them to work when they do not have an idea or thought about a particular topic. Furthermore, it teaches students how to approach a problem, pitch solutions, and decide on the best action. Table 6 depicts the 4C's of 21st-century learning skills, with focusing on collaboration.

Table 6. ABM Skills in terms of Collaboration

Collaboration	WM	VI
1. Engagement in activities like presentations and group evaluations.	3.17	MH
2. Practices the peer conversation to enhance verbalize reasoning.	3.12	MH
3. Exercise flexibility in making necessary decisions to accomplish a common goal.	3.18	MH
4. Ability to express during discussion whether favorably, negatively, or respectfully.	3.09	MH
5. Demonstrate ability to work effectively and respectfully with a diverse team.	3.12	MH
6. Capability to work on tough projects and grow as a group.	3.14	MH
7. Ability to use effective communication to increase knowledge and address problems.	3.24	MH
8. Ability to create an environment with great teamwork and interaction.	3.20	MH
Composite Mean	3.16	MH

Legend: 3.26-4.00: High (H); 2.51-3.25: Moderately High (MH); 1.76-2.50: Moderately Low (ML); 1.00-1.75: Low (L); Weighted Mean (WM); Verbal Interpretation (VI)

As shown, the item that obtained the highest ranking has a 3.24 weighted mean and is verbally interpreted as moderately high. On the other hand, the composite mean obtained was 3.16, with an interpretation of moderately high, which measured the student's ABM skills. As pointed out in the study by Al-Kaabi (2016), collaborative learning entails more than just putting students in groups. It can be done in such a way that the classes create an environment in which students are already cooperating, necessitating knowledge of the aspects that make collaborative work successful.

3. Creativity - To equip the next generation to deal with a variety of challenges and difficulties that they may face in the future, student creative development is essential as part of the learning process. It allows students to meet challenges for which there is no clear solution, several options, the tension of ambiguity is viewed as fertile ground, and inventiveness is encouraged above rote knowledge. Presented in Table 7 are the skills of Grade 12 ABM students in terms of creativity.

Table 7. ABM Skills in terms of Creativity

Creativity	WM	VI
1. Use a wide range of idea creation techniques.	3.15	MH
2. Ability to address a crisis in transformative ways.	3.08	MH
3. Potentiality to evaluate events from various points of view.	3.09	MH
4. Open and responsive to new and diverse perspectives.	3.10	MH
5. Act on creative ideas to make a tangible and useful contribution.	3.24	MH
6. Develops positive qualities and traits within oneself, such as optimism and reliance.	3.16	MH
7. Elaborate, refine, analyze and evaluate their own ideas.	3.21	MH
8. Find opportunities within problems and make the imagination work to use information.	3.19	MH
Composite Mean	3.15	MH

Legend: 3.26-4.00: High (H); 2.51-3.25: Moderately High (MH); 1.76-2.50: Moderately Low (ML); 1.00-1.75: Low (L); Weighted Mean (WM); Verbal Interpretation (VI)

According to the result, the item that came in with the highest ranking has a 3.24 weighted mean and is verbally interpreted as moderately high. Correspondingly, the least weighted mean encompassed by all indicators is 3.08, with a verbal interpretation of moderately high. It showed that respondents' levels of creativity were moderately high, resulting in a composite mean of 3.15. This signifies that the skills in terms of creativity acquired by grade 12 ABM students are a must-have for college readiness and taking an accounting degree. In relation to the study of Fatra and Maryati (2017), someone with creative skills will be effective in learning, community, profession, and life.

4. Communication - The communication skills must improve to provide themselves with adequate presentation expertise. It is the ability to effectively communicate one's own point of view as well as the ability to hear, interpret, and immediately respond to another person's point of view. Presented in Table 8 are the skills of Grade 12 ABM students in terms of communication.

Table 8. ABM Skills in terms of Communication

Communication	WM	VI
1. Use communication for a range of purposes, such as compelling to win.	3.26	H
2. Articulate thoughts and ideas effectively using oral, written, and nonverbal communication skills.	3.20	MH
3. Communication effectively with people with shared goals and responsibilities.	3.29	H
4. Listen effectively to decipher meaning.	3.30	H
5. Respond appropriately to others' opinions and perspectives.	3.31	H
6. Ability to explain one's own viewpoint.	3.22	MH
7. Develop and make use of communication skills in preparation for college and a future career.	3.27	H
8. Clarify opinions and deliver coherent directives.	3.29	MH
Composite Mean	3.15	MH

Legend: 3.26-4.00: High (H); 2.51-3.25: Moderately High (MH); 1.76-2.50: Moderately Low (ML); 1.00-1.75: Low (L); Weighted Mean (WM); Verbal Interpretation (VI)

Based on the result, the item that obtained the highest ranking has a 3.31 weighted mean and is verbally interpreted as high. The least weighted mean is 3.20, which is verbally interpreted as moderately high. Specifically, the obtained composite mean was 3.27, with an interpretation of high, which measured the student's ABM skills. This signifies that the skills in communication gained by grade 12 ABM students are essential to being college-ready and taking an accounting degree. Interaction in the classroom usually involves students decoding ideas communicated by the teacher. According to Alrashidi and Phan (2015), the likelihood that a teaching and learning engagement will be successful inside a classroom strongly depends on how well the teacher and students can transmit or exchange ideas and information. It must be improved by focusing on the ability to explain their viewpoint successfully because it is specifically created to introduce students to techniques for increasing their effectiveness in hearing lectures, reading academic texts, and planning, all of which could inhibit academic success due to the students' poor organization and expression (Komba, 2016).

Relationship between the readiness of ABM grade 12 students and ABM skills

Table 9. Relationship between the Key Cognitive Strategies and ABM Skills of Grade 12 Students

Variables	Computed Value	Significance Level	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
Critical Thinking	.444	0.000	Significant	Reject
Collaboration	.490	0.000	Significant	Reject
Creativity	.473	0.000	Significant	Reject
Communication	.553	0.000	Significant	Reject

Legend: Significant – Less than 0.05; Not Significant – More than 0.05

Table 9 presents the relationship between the readiness of grade 12 ABM students in terms of key cognitive strategies under four facets of college readiness and the skills of ABM in terms of critical thinking, collaboration, creativity, and communication. The measured results between the skills and key cognitive strategies convey a significant level of 0.000. There is a significant relationship between skills and key cognitive strategies. Hence, with the computed values, it connotes that there is a strong correlation. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 10. Relationship between the Key Content Areas and ABM Skills of Grade 12 Students

Variables	Computed Value	Significance Level	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
Critical Thinking	.429	0.000	Significant	Reject
Collaboration	.481	0.000	Significant	Reject
Creativity	.487	0.000	Significant	Reject
Communication	.561	0.000	Significant	Reject

Legend: Significant – Less than 0.05; Not Significant – More than 0.05

Table 10 highlights the significant relationship between the readiness of Grade 12 ABM students concerning key content areas under the four facets of college readiness and critical thinking, collaboration, creativity, and communication under the skills of ABM. From the abovementioned findings, the measured result yields a significant level of 0.000.

There is a significant relationship between key content areas and skills. The relationship is a strong correlation based on the computed values from the table. Further, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 11. Relationship between the Academic Behaviors and ABM Skills of Grade 12 Students

Variables	Computed Value	Significance Level	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
Critical Thinking	.413	0.000	Significant	Reject
Collaboration	.453	0.000	Significant	Reject
Creativity	.463	0.000	Significant	Reject
Communication	.562	0.000	Significant	Reject

Legend: Significant – Less than 0.05; Not Significant – More than 0.05

As the results suggest, measuring if there is a relationship between academic behavior and critical thinking, collaboration, creativity and communication yields a significant level of 0.000. Hence, there is a significant relationship. Given the respective computed values, it shows a strong correlation resulting in the null hypothesis being rejected.

Table 12. Relationship between the Contextual Skills and Awareness and ABM Skills of Grade 12 Students

Variables	Computed Value	Significance Level	Verbal Interpretation	Decision on Ho
Critical Thinking	.440	0.000	Significant	Reject
Collaboration	.496	0.000	Significant	Reject
Creativity	.488	0.000	Significant	Reject
Communication	.526	0.000	Significant	Reject

Legend: Significant – Less than 0.05; Not Significant – More than 0.05

As shown in Table 12, it reveals a significant relationship between the readiness of ABM grade 12 students in terms of contextual skills and awareness under four facets of college readiness and ABM skills in terms of critical thinking, collaboration, creativity, and communication. The results of testing the relationship between contextual skills and awareness and skills revealed a significant level of 0.000. This implies that there is a significant relationship, while the computed values show that there is a strong correlation between them. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Challenges of ABM students

ABM students nowadays encounter challenges daily, whether they are physical or mental. Difficulties in understanding, problem solving, time management, and schoolwork are the most common problems that they experience today. These difficulties result in a lack of knowledge on the subject topics and low academic performance, which can eventually affect their readiness to take an accounting degree in college. However, encountering these challenges provides experience, which is one of several ways to improve their study habits and their intelligence. Students will be able to make fewer mistakes, accomplish greater achievements, and set new goals as a result of the knowledge they obtain. Ballado-Tan (2014) asserted that, regardless of students' high aspirations for accounting, they may struggle to attain successful outcomes if their capabilities do not correspond.

The challenges ABM students encountered got a composite mean of 2.67 and were verbally interpreted as often. This means that ABM students experience these situations often, which affect their academic performance. According to Modise (2016), books and teachers' qualifications are the primary issues. The ABM strand is complex for students because of various variables, such as a lack of intellectual and numerical skills and inefficient teaching techniques used by their teachers. The study by Martin et al. (2020) reveals that students had problems journalizing the entries, analyzing the transactions, and having difficulty with related accounting subjects. With that, establishing a strong foundation for academic matters, such as self-motivation and good study behaviors, can help them cope with and surpass these challenges, which will serve as the key ingredient to students' success (Alvarado et al., 2019).

Table 13. Challenges of ABM students

Challenges of ABM Students	WM	VI
1. I have difficulties in understanding a mathematical concept.	2.82	O
2. I cannot easily answer and solve accounting calculation.	2.71	O
3. I am confused with journalizing and unsure whether to put accounting elements between debit or credit.	2.77	O
4. I am unsure and experiencing conflicts in balancing the chart of accounts in the general ledger.	2.77	O
5. Lack of teachers competent in teaching, which leads to students' poor comprehension.	2.47	S
6. Lack of knowledge in terms of concepts and theories regarding accounting related subjects	2.68	O
7. Insufficient time in reviewing and browsing lecture materials, books, and lessons	2.69	O
8. Lack of understanding in any accounting transactions	2.60	O
9. Lack of educational resources and facilities	2.57	O
10. Lack of problem exercises and information resources	2.60	O
Composite Mean	2.67	

Legend: 3.26-4.00: Always (A); 2.51-3.25: Often (O); 1.76-2.50: Sometimes (S); 1.00-1.75: Seldom (SE); Weighted Mean (WM); Verbal Interpretation (VI)

Action Plan for ABM Grade 12 Students' Preparedness in Taking Accounting Degree Rationale

An action plan outlines the requirements we must carry out in order to reach our goal. It involves setting the areas of concern, analyzing the goals, determining the activities needed to reach the goals, figuring out who are the persons involved, agreeing on a timeline for action, identifying success indicators, finalizing the plan, and assessing the outcomes. The action plan outlines a number of strategies that will be carried out with the assistance of people who are proficient in the area of ABM, such as principals, teachers, and students. The action plan will also be provided to them to implement necessary activities that can strengthen the students' skills and readiness, which can eventually help them to be more equipped when they take their college degree. The high school seniors' administration may also review and evaluate it for a better outcome. Thus, through evaluation and other methods, the strategies will be evaluated to see if they were successful and what needs to be improved.

The action plan must be carried out reasonably and should be considered in the overall evaluation. Even if the action plan provided is excellent, it is only effective if the act to be performed is present. The action plan relies on the cooperation and collaboration of the students and teachers in public schools. Thus, students and teachers contribute to accomplishing the action plan's goals and objectives.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The Grade 12 ABM students' extent of readiness in terms of their cognitive strategies, content knowledge, academic behavior, and contextual skills and awareness were strongly agreed upon.
2. The results revealed that the Critical Thinking, Collaboration, Creativity and Communication skills were moderately high, which are necessary for the course and that can help the students to be successful in their chosen accounting degree.
3. The four facets of college readiness appeared to have a strong correlation with 4C's of 21st-century learning skills.
4. ABM students encountered lot of challenges when learning ABM major subjects. They found it difficult to understand mathematical concepts and conflicts in accounting activities.
5. Implementing the proposed action plan can help the students become more academically prepared and college ready and improve their ABM skills.

From the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are forwarded:

1. The proposed action plan may be endorsed to ABM teachers, school administrators, and accounting professors for further checking and validation.
2. The proposed action plan for ABM Grade 12's preparedness in taking an accounting degree may be implemented by the public senior high schools.
3. This study may be replicated to include the profile of the respondents and private schools as the subject of the study. Teachers may be considered as one of the respondents. They might seek another framework for college readiness and ABM skills.
4. This study may be used as a basis to develop future programs to provide proper guidance for ABM students in taking an accounting degree in college.
5. Future researchers may conduct more in-depth studies to enhance the findings and improve the study through the use of the framework Facets of College Readiness and 4Cs Skills but with a different approach, such as including teachers and adding private schools as respondents.

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Appendix

Appendix A. Four Facets of College Readiness

Areas of Concern	Objectives	Activities	Persons Involved	Timeline	Success Indicators	
Key Cognitive Strategies	1. Teach students how their brains are wired for growth.	Classroom Approach: Meta-cognition, Nurturing Self-Awareness in the Classroom	Teacher and Students	Monthly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess students' cognitive development using the grade system and quiz results. Monitoring students' oral presentations and participating class discussions. Observation of students' assignments written responses. 	
	2. Give students practice recognizing what they do not understand.					
3. Provide opportunities to reflect on coursework.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Oral presentation Debate Interviews Open-Ended Questions 					
4. Facilitate reflexive thinking.						
Key Content Knowledge	1. Apply to classroom tasks requiring decision-making and critical thinking in complex situations.	Learning Techniques: "Scenario-based learning"	Teacher and Students	Monthly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students must apply their subject knowledge, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities in a safe, real-world setting. Keep track of students' work in a case and let them draw their own conclusions from what they are drawn through the story and have autonomy in how they approach their learning. Set a challenge for students and show the consequences of each decision that requires the learner to think more deeply. 	
	2. Peer-review the discussion of the scenario to ensure that it flows in the way you expect, and achieve the outcomes you intended.					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Problem Solving Case Digest Brainstorming Solving Real World Scenario Think – Pair – Share
	3. Enhance learner engagement due to the depiction of real-life situations, making learning relatable.					
Key Content Knowledge	1. Encourage learners to use their newly-acquired information.	Classroom Approach: Enhancing the Knowledge Retention in Various courses	Teacher and Students	Monthly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incorporate in interactive elements through adding quizzes, video chats, and group activities. Track their progress and to periodically review what they have learned through summative examinations. Monitor the performance tasks of students if their learning interests and subject retention are improving. 	
	2. Lead them onto follow-up courses where the recent skill will be built upon.					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quizzes Video Chats Group Activities Performance Task Summative Examinations
	3. Encourage learners to summarize what they have learned and develop their own learning material.					

Academic Behaviors	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Structure lessons to require active student involvement. Incorporate cooperative-learning opportunities into instruction. Give frequent teacher feedback and encouragement. Establish positive teacher-student relationship. 	Behavioral Conduct: Foster A Sense of Competence Through Good Academic Management <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Active participation Hands-on assignment Class Attendance Review of activities and discussion Group activities 	Teachers and Students	Monthly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Have students track data and reflect on patterns that relate academic behaviors to strategies and academic performance. Supervise students' timely and accurate submission of academic activities such as projects and outputs. Use strategies like standards-based grading tied to character learning targets to track and enhance skills related to key academic behaviors.
Contextual Skills and Awareness	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Extend college and career readiness preparation by broadening what should be expected upon taking an accounting degree. Provide them ideas of the Do's and Don'ts upon entering college. 	The Future that Awaits You: Contextual Skills and Awareness Seminar <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Seminars Open Forum Discussion Evaluation Programs 	Teacher / Speaker and Students	April	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Survey to get feedback and opinions on how the meeting went. Encourage students to participate in the open forum discussion by asking additional questions and information..
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Present them the expected course outline and syllabus within the accounting degree. Provide learning outcomes, expectations, procedures, course schedule, and other information students may need. Clarify all reasonable questions students might have relative to the course subjects, as well as their expectations. 	School to School Engagement <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Distribution of Course Handouts Face-to-Face discussion and oral presentation of the course and syllabus Open forum discussion 	Teacher and Students	May (Second Semester)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the curriculum and achieve an effective learning environment. Summarizing, reviewing, and demonstrating their understanding of the syllabus.

Appendix B. 4C's of 21st Century Skills

Areas of Concern	Objectives	Activities	Persons Involved	Timeline	Success Indicators
Critical Thinking	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Seek new ideas to broaden understanding based on the information provided. Demonstrate depth and breadth of knowledge of the course Provide students with the opportunity to synthesize knowledge and experience gained throughout the activity. 	Culminating activity: Let's Think Outside the Box <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Debate Reading and Critiquing Problem Solving Data Analysis Think Pair Share 	Teachers and Students	November (First Semester)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exposing students to various problem solving and case analysis. Increase students' learning processes through attention and observation. Evaluate whether the learner is able to integrate and apply their learning.
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Provide information that can add depth to students' understanding on different topics. Cultivate more interdisciplinary thinking, which can improve creativity and problem-solving skills. Increase students' literacy with connections to a source, to self, and to the world 	Film Viewing: Let's Watch and Learn Business Documentaries and Movie <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Course Related Film Viewing Think-Pair-Share Reflective Writing 	Teachers and Students	Every end of semester	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expand students' map of reality and become a more well-rounded person in how they view the world. Articulate important lessons learned from the documentary. Encourage students' participation through sharing their learnings and reflective writing.
Collaboration	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Involve students in a wide range of collaborative experiences to teach them how to work together and encourage one another. Set students up for successful peer collaboration. Exposure to and an increase in understanding of diverse perspectives. 	Implementation of "Buddy System" <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Think-Pair-Share Problem Solving Case Studies Oral Recitation 	Teachers and Students	Once a month	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grading students' collaboration through providing rubrics in peer or group work assessment. Providing a checklist for peer assessment and self-assessment to test how a student collaborates within a peer or group. Observation of how students project themselves and how they answer direct questions regarding peer or group activities provided.

Creativity	1. Display students' self-confidence and expressiveness through presentations of case analysis and business plan	ABM Caravan: Uplift Creativity Through Entrepreneurial Skills	Teachers and Students	February (Second Semester)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students must demonstrate their understanding by delivering presentations using the rubrics provided. Assess students' creativity by grading them whether they think differently than conventionally demanded to generate new ideas.
	2. Involve students in activities that require creative ideas and techniques to boost their creativity.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business Plan Presentation Implementing Business Plan Selling Products 			
	1. Guiding students to look at things from different perspectives.	Classroom Approach: Adding Value Through Creative Thinking	Teachers and Students	Monthly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Observation of how students react to and respond to events from diverse perspectives. Integrate activities such as essay and reflection. Providing guidelines and rubrics for presenting debates in a fair manner.
	2. Exposing students to a variety of events that necessitates in-depth understanding.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Debate Writing Essay Educational Games Artwork 			
	3. Involving students to debates addressing different crisis or scenarios.				
Communication	1. Discover different communication styles.	School Event: Communication with Diplomacy and Tact. A Way for Communicating Professionally and Effectively	Teachers and Students	February (Second Semester)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluate students' language comprehension to gauge their proficiency in written and oral mediums of communication. Providing participative activities through essay writing, debate, speeches and interviews. Monitor student's ability to accurately and clearly communicate their thoughts in the most effective and acceptable manner as possible.
	2. Demonstrate professionalism in terms of communication.				
	3. Increase students' confidence and self-esteem to express their thoughts and opinions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Writing essay Debates Sales speech Impromptu Research or case study presentations Question and answer portion regarding topics Sharing insights and takeaways 			
	4. Provide students a fundamental understanding of communication techniques.				

Appendix C. Challenges of ABM Students

Areas of Concern	Objectives	Activities	Persons Involved	Timeline	Success Indicators	
Challenges	1. Provide students with various lectures and tutorials fostering accounting theories and concepts.	Creating a Facebook page: "Act-Count-Think Silid-Aralan Series"	Researchers and Students	Monthly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Be able to finish the tasks easily, and they can cope with the topic that they find difficult. Assessment tests in every subject. Equipped with skills and knowledge by watching video lectures, and provided materials and assessments that students in college can use. 	
	2. Provide learning activities and test banks that tackle all accounting areas.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Posting theoretical questions and problems Supplemental videos Reading Materials 				
	3. Develop personal, analytical, and comprehension skills through accounting materials provided.					
	4. Design and craft the appropriate materials to utilize, such as test banks and video tutorials.					
	5. Highlight key concepts while providing a beginner's guide to debit and credit transactions.					
	1. Allow students and teachers to exchange ideas and opinions in order to produce a better quality of learning.	Open Forum: A Tool for student and Teacher Interaction	Teachers and Students	Monthly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Student feedback was gathered through paper evaluation questionnaires completed to evaluate their teacher. Engaging in conversation, starting threads, and participating regularly. Teachers can communicate quickly and efficiently with their students by asking. Get a new perspective and immediate feedback from the students. 	
	2. Enrich the learning environment by giving everyone equal opportunity to share their ideas with their teacher.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exchanging ideas Recitation Recap of topics Sharing key takeaways 				
	3. Encourage students to give constructive feedback and suggestions.					